

Kinetics and Mechanism of Chlorination of Aliphatic Amines by Sodium *N*-Chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide

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The kinetics of chlorination of aliphatic amines by sodium *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide (Chloramine-T) in the buffered medium of pH 7.4 have been carried out at 30°. The reaction showed first order dependence on [Chloramine-T] and fractional order dependence on [Amine]. The influences of neutral salt, *p*-toluenesulphonamide, dielectric constant and temperature on the rate of reaction are studied. Thermodynamic and kinetic parameters are evaluated. The results indicate the formation of a complex in a fast equilibrium step followed by slow decomposition of the complex. A rate equation and plausible mechanism consistent with the observed results are given.

AMINES find many applications in chemical industries. There has been a number of studies on the reactions between amines and halogenating agents. *N*-Halogenoamines have been obtained by the reaction of primary and secondary amines with hypohalites^{1,2}. Chloramine-T (CAT), one of the important *N*-haloamines acts both as an oxidising agent and also as chlorinating agent³⁻⁵. Kinetics of chlorination of aromatic amines by CAT has been studied^{6,7}. In view of making use of kinetic data in the analytical estimation of these compounds, it was felt interesting to study the kinetics and mechanism of chlorination of amines by CAT. The present communication deals with the kinetics and mechanism of chlorination of aliphatic amines by CAT in buffer medium of pH 7.4.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. Amines were fractionated before use. Buffer solution of pH 7.4 was prepared from sodium hydroxide and dihydrogen phosphate.

All experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order condition by keeping [Amine] in large excess over [CAT]. The amine was accurately weighed and transferred to a well stoppered flask. Ethanol (25 ml) and NaOH-KH₂PO₄ buffer (pH 7.4, 25 ml) were then added and the mixture was maintained at the required temperature. The solution of CAT was prepared by taking the requisite amount in a 100 ml volumetric flask containing ethanol (50 ml) and buffer solution (50 ml). The CAT solution (50 ml) also maintained at the same temperature, was transferred quickly to the amine solution. The reaction was followed by withdrawing samples (5 ml) and quenching in a freshly prepared

potassium-iodide solution (5%, 5 ml). To the quenched solution, 5 *N* sulphuric acid (10 ml) was added and the liberated iodine was estimated with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. A blank experiment was performed under identical conditions without the amines, negligible decomposition (1-2%) of CAT was noticed even after 30 h at 30°. The reaction was studied upto 80% completion. The first order rate constant values were computed from the plots of $\log a/(a-x)$ vs time. The values were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

Reaction mixtures containing excess of [CAT] over [Amine] were kept at 30° in buffer solution (pH 7.4) for 48 h. Estimation of the unreacted CAT showed that one mole of CAT equivalent to one mole of amine reacted according to the stoichiometric equation.

The presence of *N*-chloramine in the reaction product was confirmed by ir spectra⁸ (Found: Cl, 33%-volumetric procedure in the case of *n*-butylamine¹⁰). The sulphonamide was identified by paper chromatography and nmr spectra.

Results

Chlorination of ethylamine, butylamine, hexylamine, octylamine and diethylamine with CAT was carried out at 30° in both acid and alkaline media (pH 1-10). The reaction was too slow to measure the rate except in buffer solution of pH 7.4. Therefore, a detail kinetic investigation of the chlorination of aliphatic amines with CAT was made in buffer solution of pH 7.4. The kinetic data were obtained for all the amines. However, as the results are similar only representative data are given.

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Dependence of rate on [CAT]: The kinetics of chlorination of amines by CAT was investigated with various initial concentrations ($1-5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of CAT at 30° . In presence of excess of amines, the order of reaction with respect to [CAT] was unity, from a linear plot of $\log a/(a-x)$ vs time (Fig. 1). The constancy of the value of rate constant for different initial concentrations of CAT calculated from the integrated rate equation (Table 1) gave further evidence for the pseudo-first order dependence of rate on [CAT].

Fig. 1. Typical first order plots for the chlorination of amines by Chloramine-T; solvent 50% ethanol, pH 7.4, temp. 30° , [CAT] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, (A, B, D) [Amine] = $0.03 M$, (C) [Amine] = $0.01 M$: (A) butylamine, (B) ethylamine, (D) diethylamine and (O) octylamine.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON RATE CONSTANT

Temp. = 30° Buffer in 50% ethanol (pH 7.4)					
[Butylamine] $\times 10^3 M$	CAT $\times 10^3 M$	k $\times 10^3 s^{-1}$	[Butylamine] $\times 10^3 M$	CAT $\times 10^3 M$	k $\times 10^3 s^{-1}$
1.0	1.0	4.77	1.0	1.5	6.54
1.5	1.0	5.82	1.0	2.0	6.61
2.0	1.0	6.69	1.0	2.5	6.49
2.5	1.0	7.27	1.0	3.0	6.58
3.0	1.0	7.68	1.0	5.0	6.48
1.0	1.0	4.65 ^a	1.0	1.0	4.81 ^b

^a In presence of $NaClO_4$ ($I=0.25$). ^b In presence of PTS ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$).

Dependence of rate on [Amine]: The dependence of the rate on the various concentrations of amine is summarised in Table 1. An increase in [Amine] without change in [CAT] increased the rate of reaction. However, the linearity of a plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [Amine]$ showed the fractional order dependence of rate on the concentration of amine. The rate of chlorination of primary amine was much greater than the rate of chlorination of secondary

amine (Fig. 1). The rate of reaction was also slightly affected by the chain length of the amine (Fig. 2). The rate of chlorination of amines was in the order, decylamine > octylamine > hexylamine > butylamine > ethylamine > diethylamine.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the rate on chain length of amine; solvent 50% ethanol, pH 7.4, temp. 30° , [CAT] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Amine] = $0.03 M$.

Effect of temperature: Effect of temperature in the range $30-50^\circ$ on the rate of chlorination of amines ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) by CAT ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) was studied. From the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 3), energy (E_a), heat (ΔH^*), entropy (ΔS^*) and free energy (ΔG^*) of activation were evaluated and summarised

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$; [CAT] = $0.001 M$, [Amine] = $0.005 M$, solvent in buffer pH 7.4 (50% ethanol): (A) ethylamine, (B) butylamine, (C) hexylamine, (D) octylamine and (E) n-decylamine.

in Table 2. There is substantial variation in $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ among the amines studied, but the values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ remained virtually constant.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

[Amine] = 5×10^{-3} M; [CAT] = 1×10^{-3} M
Buffer in 50% ethanol (pH 7.4)

Amine	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Ethyl-	58.4	50.68	165.1	100.7
Butyl-	50.0	47.58	173.4	100.1
Hexyl-	47.1	44.31	181.8	100.3
Octyl-	44.8	41.88	188.7	99.0
Decyl-	41.6	39.11	195.9	98.4

Effect of solvent, ionic strength and p-toluenesulphonamide: The influence of dielectric constant (D) of the medium on the kinetics of chlorination of amines was studied by adding ethanol to the reacting system. The rate of chlorination increased slightly with increase in the ethanol composition. The plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ was linear (Fig. 4) with a positive slope in each case.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ in ethanol-water during chlorination of butylamine by Chloramine-T; [Amine] = 0.02 M, [CAT] = 1×10^{-3} M, temp. 30°, pH 7.4.

The effect of change in ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate was negligible (Table 1). The reaction was also carried out at 30° with initially added (5×10^{-4} M) p-toluenesulphonamide to know the effect of product on the reaction rate. The reaction rate was not affected by the presence of p-toluenesulphonamide (Table 1).

Discussion

CAT gives several oxidising as well as chlorinating species in aqueous solution. The stability of each species depends on the nature and pH of the

medium. In alkaline solution RNCl^- and RNHCl are present as active species^{1,1}. Comparable kinetic studies on the amine-HOCl and amine-dichloramine-T in alkaline solution have been made and compared with the results of those of the amine-CAT system⁶. These results showed that dichloramine-T and HOCl are not the reacting species in alkaline medium. They have concluded that RNHCl is the effective chlorinating agent even in slightly alkaline medium.

We summarise the conclusions from our study, (i) the reaction involves 1:1 stoichiometry, (ii) fractional order dependence on [Amine], indicating the formation of an intermediate complex, (iii) a small positive effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate, suggesting a neutral-neutral molecule or an ion-neutral molecule type of interaction in the rate determining step. The following mechanism may be postulated.

The rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{X}] \quad (1)$$

Assuming, $[\text{CAT}] = [\text{RNHCl}] + [\text{X}]$, with $[\text{R}'\text{NH}_2] \gg [\text{CAT}]$, then

$$[\text{X}] = \frac{K[\text{CAT}][\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]}{1 + K[\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]} \quad (2)$$

Substituting the value of [X] in equation (1)

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K[\text{CAT}][\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]}{1 + K[\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]} \quad (3)$$

The above proposed reaction mechanism and the rate equation (3) explain the observed results. Rearranging equation (3),

$$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{k_1[\text{CAT}]} + \frac{1}{k_1 K[\text{CAT}][\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]}$$

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{1}{k_1 K[\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) predicts a linearity between $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{R}'\text{NH}_2]$ with constant [CAT]. This is realised experimentally (Fig. 5). From the intercept and slope, the values of k_1 and K were evaluated for n-butylamine and found to be 1.1×10^{-4} and 7.5×10 , respectively.

Possibly the intermediate complex (X) involves some kind of loose association (probably electrostatic) between the slightly positive chlorine of the RNHCl molecule and the lone-pair electrons on the amine nitrogen. This association should be strong enough to prevent delocalisation of the nitrogen lone-pair into the ring. Passage to the transition state involves synchronous N-Cl bond making and N-N bond breaking in the amine molecule and vice versa in the RNHCl molecule. The intermediate

Fig. 5. Plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{Amine}]$; temp. 80° , solvent 50% ethanol, pH 7.4.

complex and the subsequent movement of electrons may be represented as follows⁹.

The mechanism is in accordance with the substantial negative entropy of activation and strong positive free energy of activation. The slightly positive dielectric constant effect observed in the present system may be due to the influence of solvent on the equilibrium step prior to the rate determining step. The constancy in $\Delta G^\ddagger$ may be explained in terms of isokinetic relationship. According to this principle, for a series of homologous substances of slightly different structures, but undergoing reaction by the same mechanism, $\Delta G^\ddagger$ will be the same with relative changes in $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$. This also confirms the unified mechanism proposed.

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